

Table 1 Summary of the most relevant journals in research quality and transparency in applied linguistics research.

Journal	TP	TC	Most cited article	Times cited	Publisher
<i>Language Learning</i>	23	2195	Plonsky & Oswald (2014)	1,490	Wiley
<i>Language Teaching</i>	15	241	Gass (2021)	74	Cambridge UP
<i>Research Methods in Applied Linguistics</i>	12	127	Larsson et al. (2023)	44	Elsevier
<i>Journal of Second Language Studies</i>	7	4	Sterling et al. (2025)	2	John Benjamins
<i>Studies in Second Language Acquisition</i>	6	113	Freeborn et al. (2023)	59	Cambridge UP
<i>System</i>	6	172	Bestgen (2017)	61	Elsevier
<i>ReCALL</i>	5	54	Burston (2022)	41	Cambridge UP
<i>Annual Review of Applied Linguistics</i>	4	195	Oswald & Plonsky (2010)	160	Cambridge UP
<i>Modern Language Journal</i>	4	325	Zhang (2019)	212	Wiley
<i>Applied Linguistics Review</i>	3	29	Wei (2024)	13	De Gruyter